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“Inclusion of Economics Textbooks in Curriculum: The case of an Almaty School”

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Abstract

The present study seeks to evaluate a new series of economics textbooks currently developed for use in the Kazakhstan secondary school - International College of Continuing Education (ICCE), Almaty. Data was collected using hard copy questionnaire filled by 122 respondent and analyzed using econometrics tools and Stata program. Two hypothesis were tested and several multiple regressions were developed based on the data collected. Regressions were tested for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and normality assumptions showing that there are no severe problems and received conclusions are statistically significant and can be trusted. New approach for textbooks evaluation process were developed and tested in practice.

Key words: teaching economics; textbooks evaluation; secondary school; econometrics; multiple regression;

Introduction and objective

The question of whether and how to use textbooks in teaching economics subjects has long been debated among professionals in this field. However, even with the development of new technologies that allow for higher quality materials, demand for textbooks continues to grow, and the publishing industry responds with new series and textbooks each year (*Garinger 2002*).

However, many teachers argue that despite the important role of textbooks, they are not always professionally designed and do not always fit the curriculum and closely correspond with the aims of the teaching program and the needs of the students (*Minh, 2007*). According to *Garinger (2002)*, *Cunningsworth, Sheldon and Skierso* have advocated a variety of approaches to textbook selection, but in practice, the process is often based on personal preference and may be affected by factors unrelated to pedagogy. Thus, textbooks should be carefully evaluated and selected before being used for a learning program.

The present study seeks to evaluate a new series of economics textbooks currently developed for use in the Kazakhstan secondary school - International College of Continuing Education (ICCE)¹³¹, Almaty. Training manuals have been developed on the basis of special courses on the basics of economics literacy by Kozlov V.N. and Kovaleva I.V. They are: the manual for grades 7-9: "Fundamentals of Economics"; the manual for grades 10-11: "Modern economy and marketing" and the workbook for grades 7-11.

In this paper by means of using student questionnaires co-authors of this books examine the efficiency of implementing manuals into the educational process of the ICCE. The aim is to analyze advantages and disadvantages of the books, understand the attitude of students towards them and pupils' expectations from implementation of manuals. As well, to obtain recommendations from students on improving manuals and determine the level of motivation of pupils to study economics in the ICCE. Based on this information will be determined the desirability of inclusion of the textbooks in the curriculum of ICCE.

State-of the-art literature review

Development and production of textbooks is a continuous process, which needs continuous and rigorous research and development. Textbook analysis is not an easy task as it includes several processes (*Skopinskaja, 2003*). *Saville-Troike (1982)* suggests a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods of content analysis. Although *Fraenkel (1996)* and *Saville-Troike (1982)* suggest that content analysis in textbooks is objective and reliable, *Sheldon (1988)* argues that "it is clear that textbook assessment is fundamentally a subjective, rule-of-thumb activity, and that no neat formula, grid or system will ever provide a definite yardstick". In his view, establishing uniform evaluative criteria might help to make textbook analysis more objective than it is at present (*Skopinskaja, 2003, p. 43*).

Textbook evaluation checklists are often used as the criteria of qualitative analysis. According to *Radic-Bojznic, and Topalov (2016)*, the literature on textbook analysis offers a number of checklists as evaluation criteria suggested by authors such as "*Joiner (1974), Cunningsworth (1984), Sheldon (1988), Skierso (1991), Byram (1994), Brown (2001) and Kilickaya (2004)*". They agree that evaluation checklists should have criteria referring to the physical characteristics of textbooks such as layout, logistical and organizational features, as well as those referring to methodology, aims, approaches to teaching and cultural information (*Radic-Bojznic, B., Topalov, J., 2016*).

Sheldon's evaluation guide (1988, p. 242) contains seventeen categories of suggested textbook criteria. Each category contains two to seven questions that represent "some points around which our thoughts can crystallize" (Sheldon, 1998, p. 242). While *Skierso's checklist* (1991, p. 444–452) is certainly the longest and the most encompassing one covered by the literature on textbook analysis. The updated version is eight pages long and certain sections and topics for consideration are used and modified by other authors. *Skierso* (1991) identifies a number of elements that need to be determined before the analysis is carried out, which contain necessary information on students, teachers and the educational institutions. She supports *Cunningworth's* (1995) idea of an impressionistic evaluation or first-glance evaluation as a survey that could help eliminate inappropriate or unsuitable textbooks from the selection process (*Skierso*, 1991, p. 435).

On the other hand, *Brown* (2001, p. 142) suggests an evaluation form that can be used as a practical set of criteria for either choosing a textbook for a course or evaluating the textbook that is currently used. *Brown* (2001) checklist is regarded as the most comprehensive one by many as it includes both general and specific criteria of textbook analysis. While *Sheldon* (1988, p. 237) states that the selection of a textbook indicates a significant "administrative and educational decision in which there is considerable professional, financial and even political investment" and therefore it is of vital importance to establish the criteria of textbook analysis. However, according to *Cunningsworth* (1995, p. 7), one should make sure that "careful selection is made, and that the materials selected closely reflect (the needs of the learners and) the aims, methods, and values of the teaching program".

Research methodology and data collection tool

For the purpose of textbook analysis, an in-depth evaluation of the manual for grades 7-9: "Fundamentals of Economics"; and a manual for grades 10-11: "Modern economy and marketing" and their accompanying workbook was conducted using the questionnaire provided by *Garinger* (2002) and *Dubovitskaya* (2002), with some modifications.

So that, the major method employed in this project about advisability of manuals implementation in learning process includes pupil's questionnaire (quantitative method). Pupils observation enabled to collect information about student's motivation to study economics literacy course and their opinions about the quality as well as feasibility of implementation of the new manuals in the learning process of the ICCE.

In designing the observation the author was interested in being able to quantify the data as well as to receive diversified opinions and comments from the pupils. Therefore, not only multiple questions were used in the questionnaire, there were also open-ended questions to allow for as much information to be provided as possible.

To study the feasibility of the manuals implementation in ICCE was decided to use empirical data analysis. To this end, students of various classes, ages, sexes, ethnicities and levels of academic achievement were observed. The survey was written in Russian and included four parts. The first part carefully allowed for anonymity gathered background information about the respondents. The second part consisted of twenty multiple-choice questions from method of diagnostics of the orientation of educational motivation provided by *Dubovitskaya (2002)*. The third part consisted of fifteen multiple-choice questions asking the respondents to evaluate the textbooks and express their attitude towards them. The fourth part consisted of three open-ended questions asking pupils about recommendations for further manuals development; their opinion about the possible influence of books on the educational process; the reasons why they consider the economy to be important or, on the contrary, an unnecessary subject for studying at school.

The respondents of the survey were 122 Almaty students taking economic literacy course in International College of Continuous Education (ICCE). Data collection took place during March and October 2018 at the ICCE during ten regular time classes. The information collection lasted approximately 20 minutes during class time. Hard-copy questionnaire technique was used to collect the information.

The observation was conducted by the teacher of the economics literacy course and the co-author of teaching manuals Kozlov V.N. To prepare students for the upcoming observation, they were given a task to familiarize themselves with the short versions of the manuals a week before the survey was conducted.

The results of observation made during March 2018 were evaluated using the basic set of Excel functions, as well as using the multiple regression method. The statistical significance of the equations obtained were checked using the determination coefficient and the Fisher criterion. In October 2018, the second survey was conducted. It allowed to collect more detailed information about the respondents who participated in the first survey. 56 previously participated students were interviewed. As a result, was received additional background information of the respondents: how many children in the respondent's family (Children), whether the respondent went to kindergarten (Kindergarten), how many years his mother (Mother) and father (Father) studied, what is his leading hand (Left), how many hours a day a respondent sleeps (Sleep), what month he or she was born (Month), at what age the respondent went to school (Firstgrade), how many hours a week he or she has sport activities (Sport), whether the respondent studies other than English foreign languages (Languages). Below are presented analysis of the information obtained using the Stata program.

As a result of the study, confirmation or refutation of two hypotheses is expected. Firstly, it is assumed that the motivation for studying the economy is most affected by student's performance.

Secondly, it is assumed that the gender of respondents will have the greatest impact on the evaluation of books by students. Finally, it is also expected to receive an informed response to the main question of the study on the advisability of introducing the new manuals in the ICCE curriculum.

Data analysis with critical thinking and discussion

Let's start from analysis of the results of the first part of the questionnaire, it gathered background information about the respondents. The average age of the respondents is 15 years (29 pupils). The minimum age is 12 years (2 students). The maximum age is 18 years (1 respondent). Among the respondents, the female sex is 54.1% (66 girls), the male gender was 45.9% (56 boys), respectively. The greater part of respondents are representatives of Kazakh ethnicity - 43.3% (53 pupils). The second largest ethnicity group is Russian - 23.8% (29 students). The remaining 32.9% of the respondents are Korean (6.6%); Jewish (3.3%); Ukrainian, Turkish, Tatar (2.5%), and other ethnicities. Therefore, the Kazakh and Russian ethnicities were chosen to form the regression analysis equation. Respondents GPA: consists of average GPA students - 45.1% (55 pupils), above the average - 21.3% (26 respondents), below the average - 11.5% (14 children), honor - 14.8% (18 people) and poor GPA - only 7.4% (pupils) of all students.

Analysis of the second part of the questionnaire. It describe the kind and level of respondents' motivation. According to the data, the respondents are dominated by internal motivation to study the subject, 87.7% of students (107 schoolchildren) study the subject of their own volition, the remaining 12.3% (15 pupils) have an external motivation. Since motivation has predominantly an internal orientation, it has been evaluated in terms of degrees: low, high and medium. As a result, it was revealed that a low level of external motivation is observed only in 2 cases, the average in 48 cases and high in 72 cases, which is 59% of the total number of respondents. These data allow to conclude that the level of internal motivation of respondents is extremely high. As a result of the calculations, the multiple regression equation was obtained: $Y = 12.1375 + 0.04109X_1 + 1.6941X_2 - 1.5069X_3 + 2.1928X_4$. Interpretation: increase in age - X_1 per 1 unit leads to an increase in Y (motivation) by an average of 0.0411 units. Affiliation of the respondent to the female sex - X_2 leads to an increase in Y (motivation) by an average of 1.694 units. Belonging to Kazakh ethnicity - X_3 leads to a decrease in Y (motivation) on average by 1.507 units. GPA above the average - X_4 leads to an increase in Y (motivation) on average by 2.193 units. By the maximum coefficient $\beta_4 = 0.288$ conclude that the greatest influence on the result of Y (motivation) is provided by the factor X_4 (the performance is above the average). The statistical significance of the equation was verified by means of the determination coefficient and the Fisher criterion. It was found that 23.51% of the total variability of Y (motivation) is explained in the study situation by the change in X_j factors (age, sex, ethnicity, academic achievement). It is also

established that the parameters of the model are statistically significant (tested for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and normality).

Analysis of the third part - students' attitudes toward textbooks. In general, students like the manuals, but there is still something to work on. Firstly, authors may complete homework in such a way that they cause more interest. Secondly, the workbook is not as significant as it was supposed to be, it might be worth removing it, or make several copies just for library use. Thirdly, it would be nice to change the cover and design of the manuals so that more pupils would like them. It can be concluded that 66.5% of respondents (81 students) excellently graded new manuals, 23.8% of respondents (29 children) gave good grades, and only 9.8 % of students (12 people) gave bad grades. The multiple regression equation is: $Y = 4.1915 + 0.3632X_1 + 0.3885X_2 - 1.0052X_3 + 0.9455X_4$. Meaning that an increase in age - X_1 per 1 unit. leads to an increase in Y (manuals grade) by an average of 0.389 points. An affiliation of a respondent with the female sex - X_2 leads to an increase in Y (manuals grade) by an average of 0.389 points. Belonging to Kazakh ethnicity - X_3 reduces Y (manuals grade) of an average of 1.005 points. GPA above the average - X_4 leads to an increase in Y (manuals grade) on average by 0.946 points. For maximum coefficient $\beta_4 = 0.288$ conclude that the greatest influence on the result Y (manuals grade) provides X_1 factor (age). It was found that in the investigated situation, 8.05% of the total variability of Y (manuals grade) is explained by the change in the factors X_j (age, gender, ethnicity, academic achievement). It was also established that the parameters of the model are statistically significant (tested for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and normality).

Fourth part. most of the recommendations relate not to the content of the manuals, but to their general availability and presentability. Students are ready to use the manuals and will be happy about their implementation. From all this follows that the expediency of using these manuals in the process of teaching economic literacy course in the ICCE is significant. It is possible to draw a conclusion about the favorable effect of manuals on teaching economy course after their introduction.

Summary, conclusion and recommendations

Thanks to a large number of respondents of different ages, gender, ethnicities and levels of academic achievement (background), it was possible to obtain statistically significant results concerning the put forward hypotheses.

Firstly, the hypothesis that the students' motivation to study the economy is more influenced by the level of the academic performance is confirmed (first observation, March 2018). This factor has the most significant impact on student motivation, explaining 23.51% of the total variability of student motivation. However, according to the second research conducted in October 2018, another more important and significant factor was found – it is Languages (the more foreign languages pupil learns, the higher is his or her motivation to learn economics).

Secondly, the hypothesis that the sex of respondent will most affect the outcome of the assessment of books was incorrect. The age of the respondents has the greatest impact on the assessment of books by respondents (8.05%), while sex is only the third most influential factor (according to the first research – March 2018). However, according to the second observation, only two factors might influence student's assessment of the books. They are sport activities and being left-handed. Both factors have negative influence on books grading. So that left-handed student who love sport activities grades books worsen than all other students. But it should be taken into account, that second regression failed F-test, so that it is impossible to say that this information is true. It is better to make other researches, collect more information.

The statistical significance of the equations (March 2018) obtained was verified using the determination coefficient and the Fisher criterion, as a result of which it was established that the parameters of both regression models are statistically significant, and therefore they can be trusted. However, only first equation from the second observation (October 2018) may be trusted.

Thirdly, was received answer to the main question of the study on the advisability of introducing manuals in the process of teaching students the course of economics literacy in the ICCE. According to the received data 90% of the students of the ICCE have an internal motivation for studying the economy and their assessment of the benefits on average turned out to be very high. So that it can be concluded that the introduction of the manuals will have a beneficial effect on the process of teaching students. Therefore, the introduction of manuals in any form (electronic or printed) is appropriate for the administration of the college. In addition, it should be noted that the students themselves believe that these manuals will have a beneficial effect on their motivation and level of knowledge, and this also speaks in favor of the use of the manuals in the process of teaching the students to the ICCE.

Somewhat unexpected was the fact that belonging to the Kazakh ethnicity in both equations of regression models negatively affected the general motivation of students and the average assessment of manuals by them (March 2018). Perhaps this can be explained by ethnic or national characteristics, but for this conclusion it is necessary to conduct a separate, more detailed study of this factor in the future. However, according to second observation (October 2018) – ethnic residuals are insignificant and cannot be trusted.

Decisions related to textbook selection will affect teachers, students, and the overall classroom dynamic. It is probably one of the most important decisions facing educators. The use of an evaluation procedure or questionnaire can lead to a more systematic and thorough examination of potential textbooks and to enhanced outcomes for learners, instructors, and administrators. The described evaluation methodology may be used or adapted as a tool to help educators who are deciding which textbooks may be most appropriate for their classes.

So that the current project helps to identify the problems. This contribution would be of practical value to textbook authors and teachers of economics in Kazakhstan. Besides, the project focuses on a teaching context that is largely unheard of and under-represented in the economics field. Therefore, for the scholars outside Kazakhstan, the project report would be a rich source of information for their use and reference.

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